

Welcome to I SoRD14 !

The **First** International Symposium on Robust Design

Thomas J. Howard

Head of Robust Design Group

About I SoRD

The official Symposium of the Robust Design SIG*

* *An official Special Interest Group of the Design Society*

Organised by...

The Robust Design Group, DTU-Mekanik

DTU Mechanical Engineering
Department of Mechanical Engineering

Sponsored by...

Novo Nordisk
fundes of the DTU Robust Design Programme

&

Valcon Design
Pioneers of the 6 Theta[®] methodology used at DTU

Why a Symposium not a Conference

- ICoRD was already taken and ISoRD was a bit more cutting edge
- Smaller than a conference
- More topic focused than a conference
- More informal, practical, dialogue based
- The flexibility of the definition:

sym·po·si·um

/sim'pōzēəm/

noun

noun: **symposium**; plural noun: **symposia**; plural noun: **symposiums**

a conference or meeting to discuss a particular subject.

- a collection of essays or papers on a particular subject by a number of contributors.
- a drinking party or convivial discussion, especially as held in ancient Greece after a banquet (and notable as the title of a work by Plato).

Aims of the I SoRD Symposium:

“To create a regular, biennial (every 2 years), International Symposium on Robust Design. Delegates will delve deeper into the subject matter and align academic research activities and teaching with the needs and developments in industry.”

ISoRD14 Statistics

Delegates: 66 (91% Male)

Industry: 37 (57%)

Academia: 29 (43%)

Papers: 16 Accepted, receiving 2 double open reviews.

Companies present:

Universities present:

The ISoRD14 Programme

Thursday - 14th August

08:00	Bus Departs from Ibsens Hotel
09:00	Welcome Introduction Session + Keynote 1
10:00	Break
10:30	Oral Session 1 - Robustness in Design + Industry Case Paper 1
12:00	Lunch
13:00	Robust Design Workshop: A forensic engineering case
15:00	Break
	Robust Design Workshop continued.
17:00	Bus departs from Conference
20:00	Conference Dinner Nørrebro Bryghus (meet at hotel reception at 19:30)

Friday - 15th August

08:00	Bus Departs from Ibsens Hotel
08:45	Computer Aided Robust Design (CARD) Session + Keynote 2
10:15	Break
10:30	Poster Session: Robust Design Research + Industry Case Paper 2
12:00	Lunch
13:00	Oral Session 2 - Robustness in Production + Keynote 3 + Closing presentation
15:00	Farewell Drinks Reception
16:00	Bus departs from Conference
20:00	Food & Drinks, tour inc. Christiania, (meet at hotel reception at 19:30)

Name Badge

Workshop table

Workshop Final Presentation,
CARD Session Starting point,
Poster Session Starting point

Your WiFi Code is on the back!

Network: DTU

ISoRD14 working definitions

“Robust Design is a methodology for designing products so that their reliability is less sensitive to variation.”

Robustness is a Subset of Reliability. It is specifically related to reliability (and quality) issues caused by variation

$$\text{Reliability (due to variation)} = f \left(\begin{array}{l} \text{Sensitivity} \\ \text{(of the product)} \end{array}, \begin{array}{l} \text{Variation} \\ \text{(in the product)} \end{array} \right)$$

Robust Design Reduces Sensitivity

"reliable things unleash the creativity of people who then build stuff that you could not imagine."